

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPLEMENTING THE CASE METHOD IN SECONDARY GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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Annotation. The article explores the application of the Case Method in the subject of Chemistry. Just as the Case Method is applied in various fields of social life, its integration into the educational process should also be welcomed positively. Addressing complex situations requires active cognitive engagement and critical thinking. This approach represents a significant step toward the overall development and enrichment of thinking skills. There are broad opportunities for the preparation and application of case tasks across all subjects, including chemistry lessons. The essence of the Case Method lies in identifying possible solutions to a given situation, analyzing various alternatives to the existing problem, and selecting the most optimal one. In other words, this method is fundamentally centered on solving complex problems. Students are provided with case materials in the form of a “document set”, which includes a description of the situation, primary and supplementary resources, methodological guidelines and other supporting information. The fact that such problems do not have a single correct solution stimulates not only cognitive activity but also fosters a strong interest in learning among students. While working on case tasks, students predominantly acquire knowledge through their own initiative, which significantly contributes to the development of their practical skills. By engaging with various sources, students have the opportunity to apply their existing knowledge and skills, enhance their practical experience, express personal opinions and evaluate the perspectives of others.

Key words: Case Method, chemistry education, problem based learning, case technology, teaching strategies

ORTA ÜMUMTƏHSİL MƏKTƏBLƏRİNDƏ KEYS METODUNUN REALLAŞDIRILMASININ NƏZƏRİ ƏSASLARI

Annotasiya. Məqalədə keys metodunun kimya fənninə tətbiqi araşdırılır. Keys metodun cəmiyyət həyatının müxtəlif sahələrində tətbiqi kimi, onun təhsil prosesinə daxil edilməsi də müsbət qarşılanmalıdır. Qarşıya çıxan mürəkkəb vəziyyətlərin həlli yollarını tapmaq təfəkkürün fəal işləməsinə və idrakın aktivliyini zəruri edir. Bu yanaşma ümumilikdə düşüncə bacarıqlarının inkişafı və zənginləşməsi istiqamətində mühüm addımdır. Bütün fənlərdə, o cümlədən kimya dərslərində keys tapşırıqlarının hazırlanması və tətbiqi üçün geniş imkanlar mövcuddur. Keys metodunun əsas mahiyyəti situasiyadan çıxış yollarının tapılması, mövcud problemin müxtəlif həll variantlarının müəyyənləşdirilməsi və onların içərisindən ən optimal olanının seçilməsi üzərində qurulmuşdur. Yəni bu metodun təməlinə çətin vəzifələrin həlli dayanır. Şagirdlərə “sənədlər toplusu” formasında təqdim olunan keys materialları onlara situasiyanın təsviri, əsas və əlavə mənbələr, metodik göstərişlər və digər köməkçi məlumatlar bərdə məlumat verir. Bu cür problemlərin bir doğru həllinin olmaması, şagirdlərdə yalnız idrak aktivliyini deyil, eyni zamanda güclü öyrənmə marağını da stimullaşdırır. Keys tapşırıqları üzərində işləyərkən şagirdlər bilikləri əsasən öz təşəbbüsləri ilə mənimsəyirlər ki, bu da onların müxtəlif praktik bacarıqlarının formalaşmasına mühüm təsir göstərir. Müxtəlif mənbələrlə işləyən şagirdlər mövcud bilik və bacarıqlarını tətbiq etməyə, praktiki təcrübələrini artırmağa, şəxsi fikirlərini ifadə etməyə və başqalarının baxışlarını dəyərləndirməyə imkan əldə edirlər.

Açar sözlər: keys metod, kimya təhsili, problem əsaslı öyrənmə, keys texnologiya, tədris strategiyaları

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ КЕЙС МЕТОДА В ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛАХ

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается применение кейс метода на уроках химии. Так же, как кейс метод применяется в различных сферах общественной жизни, его интеграция в образовательный процесс должна восприниматься положительно. Решение сложных ситуаций требует активной когнитивной деятельности и критического мышления. Такой подход представляет собой важный шаг на пути общего развития и обогащения мыслительных навыков. Существует широкое поле для подготовки и применения кейсов во всех предметах, включая уроки химии. Суть кейс метода заключается в выявлении возможных решений конкретной ситуации, анализе различных вариантов решения существующей проблемы и выборе наиболее оптимального. Другими словами, данный метод ориентирован на решение сложных задач. Ученикам предоставляются материалы кейса в виде «набора документов», включающего описание ситуации, основные и дополнительные источники, методические рекомендации и другую вспомогательную информацию. Отсутствие единственного правильного решения таких задач стимулирует не только познавательную активность, но и повышает интерес учеников к обучению. Работа с кейсами, учащиеся преимущественно осваивают знания на основе собственной инициативы, что существенно способствует развитию их практических навыков. Взаимодействуя с различными источниками, ученики получают возможность применять имеющиеся знания и умения, повышать практический опыт, выражать личные мнения и оценивать взгляды других.

Ключевые слова: метод кейсов, химическое образование, проблемно ориентированное обучение, кейс технология, стратегии преподавания.

Unlike traditional lecture based instruction, case method classes unfold without a predetermined, detailed script. Successful implementation of this approach requires the instructor to manage both content delivery and classroom dynamics simultaneously. This necessitates thorough and systematic preparation from both a theoretical and pedagogical standpoint.

Effective application of the case method demands that educators strike a balance between structured planning and adaptive responsiveness to spontaneous developments during class. As discussions progress, instructors must skillfully identify and utilize teachable moments and multi-level cognitive opportunities, guiding students toward the development of analytical thinking and problem solving abilities.

According to Christensen, the pedagogical principles and methodological techniques of the case method are cultivated “through collaboration and cooperation with colleagues and peers, as well as through continuous self- observation and reflective practice.”

The Christensen Center for Teaching and Learning at Harvard University organizes the practical application of the case method into the following core dimensions:

Preparing to Teach- developing instructional strategies and structuring case materials

Leading in the Classroom- facilitating discussions and promoting student engagement

Providing Assessment and Feedback- evaluating student performance and delivering constructive feedback

Sample Class Models- analyzing and applying real classroom scenarios. [6]

Currently, active learning methods, including the case-study method, are widely employed in leading Russian universities to train students in economics and related disciplines. The application of this method in the economics curriculum not only enhances students interest in academic subjects,

but also contributes to a deeper understanding of economic laws, while fostering research capabilities, communication skills, and creative problem-solving.

A defining feature of the case-study method is its reliance on real-world facts to construct problem-based scenarios. Originally developed for economics educations, the case-study method has since become a valuable pedagogical tool in diverse fields such as medicine, law and other sciences.[5]

A teacher who is freed from routine, mechanical tasks can truly focus on genuine pedagogical work- that is, fostering the personal and intellectual development of students. In modern education, finding the right balance between individuality, creativity, and the use of technology is a critical and complex issue that must be addressed.

In this context, pedagogical technology refers to a system of optimal, goal-oriented didactic processes that are designed in advance based on specific parameters for use in computer-based or technologically supporting teaching. From a practical standpoint, pedagogical technology can also encompass a teacher's system of methodically developed techniques and strategies, as well as the methodology used in the educational and upbringing process.

By integrating technology into education, one of the main challenges- managing and organizing the learning process- can be effectively resolved. In contrast, traditional or "non-technological" teaching methods often suffer from several shortcomings, such as ambiguity, weak control over learning activities and subjective or episodic assessment of student understanding.[1]

Scientific concepts and situations, as well as general subject skills, are considered essential components of scientific literacy. The aim of the research is to comprehensively assess these knowledge and skills. Particularly important is the ability to identify questions within a given set that pertain to natural sciences and to draw scientifically grounded conclusions based on the provided information.

The school environment, curricula and technologies used should be adapted accordingly. The role of competency-based tasks in modern education is becoming increasingly significant. One effective way to develop students functional literacy is through the preparation and application of PISA-format tasks.

One of the approaches that helps develop such skills is the case technology method. This method enhances students abilities to analyze, self-assess, seek creative solutions, reason, defend their opinions and apply learned knowledge to real-life situations.

Case methods mainly involve problem-solving, research-oriented and project-based approaches.

Case technology or situation-solving technology, is an active learning method aimed at developing the skills needed to solve real-life problems.[2]

Although case studies are an active learning method, they are not considered games or role-playing. The goal of a case is for individuals or groups to work on solving situations, which involves analysis, gathering additional information, developing practical skills and drawing conclusions necessary for resolving the problem.[3]

This method is based on tasks aimed at developing competencies, research-oriented experimental work, and the analysis of scientific information. The curriculum should be structured in such a way that students develop the ability to explain events from a scientific perspective and work with information, prepare scientific projects, and interpret existing data and facts to draw appropriate conclusions. To assess the level of development of these competencies, tasks that are close to or derived from real-life situations are used instead of typical exercises. In order to solve such tasks, subject-specific knowledge alone is sometimes not sufficient and interdisciplinary connections are required. The application of case technology within the framework of practice-oriented teaching demonstrates a competency-based approach in education, with the aim of increasing scientific literacy.[4]

Using case-based tasks in chemistry lesson

Topic: "Pure substances and mixtures"

Case 1: “Separation of substance mixtures”

“A large amount of household waste is generated as a result of human activity. Gold, tin, aluminum and other substances can be found in household waste. Trash is a unique mixture of various components. Waste processing is a labor-intensive and expensive process, and almost no one is engaged in it for the purpose of obtaining useful materials.

Currently, there is no less labor-intensive and cost-effective alternative method of waste processing. Perhaps you can suggest methods for separating some components of household waste.”

Tasks:

“You are provided with a mixture consisting of salt, sand, iron filings and sawdust simulating waste, as well as pure samples of each component of the mixture. Try to separate this mixture using simple and effective methods. Determine the mass percentage of each component in the mixture. What do you think if copper shavings were used instead of sawdust in the mixture, would it be possible to separate the substances using different methods?

The next stage of the subject involves studying physical and chemical phenomena, with the aim of forming a clear understanding of these phenomena among students.”

Case 2: “Physical and chemical phenomena”

“Pay attention to all the processes that occur when a samovar is set up. Which of these processes would you classify as physical phenomena and which as chemical processes?

From filling the samovar with water, lighting the matches and coal, brewing tea, and adding sugar and milk to it.

Do you observe any phenomena on the copper lid of the samovar? Are there any changes in the coal?”

This type of task was given in one of the chemistry manuals for vocational schools in 1927.

Tasks:

1. Analyze the given situation.
2. Define physical and chemical phenomena.
3. Create a comparative table of the phenomena occurring in the scene.

Conclusion

These keywords help students develop fundamental knowledge of basic chemical concepts, substances, the processes they undergo, as well as the conditions and outcomes of these processes. At the same time, while studying topics such as “Chemical substance and mixtures”, students attention is drawn to environmental issues. They explore the impact of industrial, household and chemical waste on the environment, analyze their compositions and propose methods for purification, recycling or possible reuse. In response to the teacher’s question about methods of separating substances, after a brief discussion, students are able to suggest appropriate separation techniques.

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